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Linking High-Harmonic Generation and Strong-Field Ionization in Bulk Crystals

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Abstract

The generation of high-order harmonics in bulk solids subjected to intense ultra-short laser pulses has opened up new avenues for research in extreme nonlinear optics and light-matter interaction on sub-cycle timescales. Despite significant advancement over the past decade, a complete understanding of the involved phenomena is still lacking. High-harmonic generation in solids is currently understood as arising from nonlinear intraband currents, interband recollision and ionization-related phenomena. As all of these mechanisms involve or rely upon laser-driven excitation we combine measurements of the angular dependence of nonlinear absorption and high-order harmonic generation in bulk crystals to demonstrate the relation between high-harmonic

emission and nonlinear, laser-induced ionization in solids. An unambiguous correlation between the emission of harmonics and laser-induced ionization is found experimentally, that is supported by numerical solutions of the semiconductor Bloch equations and an analytical model of orientation-dependent ionization rates using maximally localized Wannier functions.

Keywords: *high-harmonic generation, strong-field ionization, plasma formation, attosecond physics, strong-field physics, ultrafast optics, nonlinear optics*

Introduction

High-order harmonic generation (HHG) in gases marked the birth of attosecond science allowing to track carrier dynamics on sub-cycle timescales.¹⁻⁴ Transferring the concept of HHG to solid-state systems⁵ has opened up several research avenues ranging from fundamental investigations of strong-field-driven carrier dynamics⁶ towards the development of compact extreme-ultraviolet (XUV) sources,⁷ petahertz electronics⁸⁻¹¹ and laser picoscopy.¹² In solids, four main sources of nonlinearity have been identified and investigated with regards to harmonic generation.

First, the Kerr-type nonlinearity¹³ based on anharmonic spatial motion of valence electrons has been invoked to explain conventional second harmonic generation (SHG) ever since Franken's seminal work¹⁴ that marked the advent of nonlinear optics. It is held responsible for low-order harmonic generation with multiple applications in frequency conversion as well as in optical-parametric chirped pulse amplification (OPCPA).¹⁵ Second, high-order harmonics extending to frequencies in the XUV¹⁶ have been associated with interband recollisions (in strong analogy with the three-step model in the atomic case^{1,2,17}). Third, high harmonics have also been explained by intraband currents where the nonlinearity enters through the non-parabolic shape of the conduction (and valence) bands.¹⁸ Fourth, the nonlinearity that is inherent to the process of photoionization was proposed as a possible origin for harmonic gen-

eration.^{19,20} Three possible ionization-related mechanisms have been discussed in the context of HHG.^{21,22} Brunel harmonics, arising from the acceleration of quasi-free carriers excited by photoionization have been analyzed in gases, clusters, bulk solids and thin films.²³⁻²⁷ Moreover, after non-resonant photoionization an excited electron has nonzero velocity which provides sub-cycle contributions to the polarization and gives rise to the generation of harmonics. However, the strength of these velocity harmonics is expected to be insignificant under typical experimental conditions due to the modest photon energies that result in small excess velocities. Finally, the previously overlooked injection current, originating from the spatial displacement of an electron wavepacket during laser-driven tunneling ionization, was identified as the dominant source of low-order harmonic generation in fused silica.^{22,28}

The highly anisotropic angular dependence of the HHG process in crystalline solids has been correlated to the electronic band structure,^{16,29,30} petahertz photocurrents,³¹ real-space trajectories of electronic wavepackets^{32,33} and van-Hove singularities.^{34,35} Low-order (below-bandgap) harmonic emission has been associated with intraband dynamics while above-bandgap HHG is generally attributed to interband recollision.^{31,36} In recent experimental investigations conducted on GaAs, it was observed that the absorption of the fundamental mid-infrared radiation reached its maximum when the crystal orientations were aligned to minimize the harmonic yield. Concurrently, nonlinear phenomena associated with cross-polarized waves were identified as the driving factors behind modifications in the anisotropic HHG emission.³⁷ Strong laser fields that are sufficient for HHG and above-threshold ionization in gases have been demonstrated to create coherent excited states,³⁸ also motivating simultaneous investigations of strong-field absorption and HHG in solids.

All of the aforementioned HHG mechanisms - except for the Kerr-type nonlinearity - rely either on the presence or on the excitation of quasi-free conduction band electrons and valence band holes. In the most common experimental scheme the photon energy of the driving near-infrared or mid-infrared laser field $\hbar\omega$ is smaller than the bandgap E_g of the irradiated

crystal. Thus, excited carriers are generated by nonlinear photoionization or electron-impact ionization.³⁹ Despite intense research in the past decade, the connection between carrier excitation and its impact on the anisotropic angular dependence of the harmonic emission has not yet been fully understood. While photoionization is often a key factor in harmonic generation, to date, there has been no detailed investigation of its angular dependence under HHG conditions.

In this article we experimentally demonstrate a correlation between orientation-dependent ionization yields and the efficiency of HHG in various bulk crystals. We combine measurements of the angular dependence of nonlinear absorption (also referred to as multiphoton crystallography^{40,41}) and angle-dependent HHG efficiencies to establish a direct link between the excitation of quasi-free carriers and the emission of high-order harmonics. We identify an unambiguous connection between intense HHG emission and strong ionization for distinct orientations in various oxide and fluoride crystals. Our experimental results are supported by numerical simulations based on the semiconductor Bloch equations (SBEs) and analytical calculations of the photoionization rate based on the Wannier formalism. Our numerical results reproduce the experimentally observed angular dependence of the harmonic emission and provide insights into the complex interplay of interband and intraband dynamics as well as the importance of ionization-related mechanisms for low-order harmonic generation.

Experimental Setup

In the experiments we used the signal beam of a home-built, high-repetition-rate, dual-beam OPCPA (100 kHz) with a central wavelength of 1500 nm and a full-width half-maximum (FWHM) pulse duration of ~ 50 fs (architecture based on the one presented in Ref.⁴²) to generate high-order harmonics from bulk crystals. The linearly polarized beam was focused to an $1/e^2$ beam diameter of ~ 50 μm (measured by the knife-edge technique in ambient air) providing a maximum peak intensity in ambient air of ~ 30 TW cm^{-2} in the focal

plane. High harmonics emitted from bulk crystals were analyzed in transmission geometry

Figure 1: Experimental setup and results obtained in a bulk MgO crystal. (a). A short-wavelength infrared (SWIR) laser pulse ($\lambda_0 = 1500 \text{ nm}$, $\tau = 50 \text{ fs}$) is focused into the bulk of a crystal mounted on a rotation stage. The harmonic radiation is analyzed using a visible-ultraviolet (VIS/UV) spectrometer. The transmitted fundamental radiation is analyzed by inserting a moveable dielectric mirror directing the SWIR beam onto a photodiode. (b). Illustrative harmonic spectra containing the third, the fifth and the seventh harmonic of the SWIR driving field obtained in a bulk MgO crystal at two different orientations ($\theta = 25^\circ$ and 45°) and a peak intensity of 18 TW cm^{-2} . The large spectral width of the seventh harmonic is attributed to spectral broadening in the detection system. (c). Absorption of the fundamental laser field for different peak intensities ($I_1 = 11 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ and $I_2 = 18 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$) below the damage threshold as a function of the orientation angle θ .

with the help of a commercial visible-ultraviolet (VIS-UV) spectrometer (Avantes AvaSpec-HS1024x58/122TEC). The energy remaining in the short-wave infrared (SWIR) signal beam was directed onto a photodiode [cf. Fig. 1(a)] with the help of a highly reflective mirror at 1500 nm . A possible contamination of the transmitted signal beam by harmonic radiation was excluded due to the low reflectivity of the dielectric mirror for the harmonic wavelengths and by the low conversion efficiencies (typically around 10^{-6} ⁴³). The crystalline samples were

mounted on a computer-controlled rotation stage enabling a precise and reproducible variation of the angle θ between the main axis of the crystal and the laser polarization axis (for further experimental details see Supporting Information).

Experimental Results

Figure 1(b) and (c) show exemplary high-harmonic spectra obtained in a 200 μm thick MgO crystal, cut along the (100) plane, at two different orientation angles ($\theta = 25^\circ$ and 45° , for minimum and maximum signal strength) and the absorption of the SWIR laser pulse as a function of θ , for two different peak intensities ($I_1 = 11 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$, $I_2 = 18 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$). The harmonic yield of all observed orders is higher for $\theta = 45^\circ$ when compared to $\theta = 25^\circ$ (the crystal angles were calibrated by perturbative third harmonic generation at a moderate excitation intensity of $\sim 2 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$, details are provided in the Supporting Information). Based on the inset shown in Fig. 1(b) illustrating the cubic crystal structure of MgO, such a yield anisotropy can be attributed to high-symmetry directions in the crystal lattice. At an angle of 45° the real space trajectories of the excited electron wavepackets point towards the nearest-neighbour of the same species (Mg-Mg or O-O) inside the crystal structure (monoatomic nearest-neighbour direction).

The SWIR absorption exhibits no pronounced θ -dependence at a low peak intensities below $\sim 8 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ (not shown). Instead, the absorption stays close to 0 after accounting for the losses due to Fresnel reflection at the interfaces ($\sim 16\%$ for MgO). At an intermediate SWIR excitation intensity of 11 TW cm^{-2} the average absorption increases to $\sim 4\%$ [yellow circles in Fig. 1(c)]. At the same time distinct extrema begin to emerge. When the excitation intensity approaches the laser-induced damage threshold of the used samples (determined to be $\sim 20 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$), the modulation amplitude of these oscillations increases and a clear eight-fold symmetry becomes apparent in the θ -dependent absorption of the SWIR pump laser pulse with maxima appearing in the diatomic ($\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270°) and monoatomic

($\theta = 45^\circ, 135^\circ, 225^\circ$ and 315°) nearest-neighbour directions.

Figure 2: Experimentally determined HHG and absorption in MgO. (a). Angular dependence of the third harmonic in the perturbative (at $I_0 = 6 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$, orange circles) and in the non-perturbative regime (at $I_0 = 18 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$, grey circles). (b). θ -dependence of the observed odd harmonics and the SWIR absorption in a $200 \mu\text{m}$ thick MgO crystal obtained at a peak intensity of 18 TW cm^{-2} . The cubic crystal structure of MgO is sketched in the background to indicate the nearest-neighbour directions. The harmonic signals as well as the absorption are normalized and offset vertically for clarity. Experimental datapoints are represented by circles while the solid lines show numerical fits according to Eq. 1. (c). Amplitudes extracted from the fit function (Eq. 1) for the observed harmonic orders as a function of the SWIR excitation intensity. (d). Average transmission and modulation amplitude of the fundamental pump laser pulse as a function of intensity. Transmission values are averaged over all orientation angles, the errorbars represent the corresponding standard deviation.

With the goal to link the nonlinear absorption and the emission of high-order harmonics, the orientation-dependent harmonic yields are compared to the nonlinear absorption in Fig. 2. Similar to the angular distribution of the absorption, the third harmonic signal exhibits an eight-fold symmetry at a SWIR peak intensity of 18 TW cm^{-2} [see dark green circles in Fig. 2(a)]. As reported in Ref.³² the maxima of the third harmonic emission along the diatomic nearest-neighbour directions ($\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270°) are suppressed at low intensity where perturbative mechanisms dominate the nonlinear response [orange circles in Fig. 2(a)]. Hence, a transition from a four-fold symmetry to an eight-fold symmetry can be observed for the third harmonic as the excitation intensity increases.

At an excitation intensity of 18 TW cm^{-2} the harmonic yield of all observed orders is maximized along the diatomic nearest-neighbour directions (Mg-O bonding directions at $\theta = 0^\circ$, 90° , 180° and 270°) as shown in Fig. 2(b). Further maxima are formed along the monoatomic nearest-neighbour directions (at $\theta = 45^\circ$, 135° , 225° and 315°) resulting in an eight-fold symmetry of all observed harmonic orders whose extrema align exactly with those of the nonlinear absorption [pink circles in Fig. 2(b)] suggesting that the harmonic emission is directly correlated with nonlinear photoionization. Due to the lower signal strength the fifth and seventh harmonic could only be observed at intensities where all orders exhibited an eight-fold symmetry. Note that in contrast to the results presented in Ref.³⁷ our orientation-dependent measurements are not affected by XPW-related effects as evidenced by the polarization measurements presented in the Supporting Information.

For further analysis the angle-dependent harmonic yields $Y(\theta)$ as well as the θ -dependent absorption are approximated by a periodic fit function according to

$$Y(\theta) = A_0 + A_{\text{dia}} * \cos[2\theta]^{2n} + A_{\text{mono}} * \sin[2\theta]^{2n}. \quad (1)$$

Here A_0 is an offset amplitude, A_{dia} and A_{mono} denote the amplitudes associated with the oscillations along the mono- and diatomic nearest-neighbour directions, respectively. The parameter n determines the width of the maxima and is well approximated by 3 throughout this work.

In Fig. 2(c) the amplitudes that were introduced in Eq. 1 are analyzed as a function of the SWIR intensity. The eight-fold angular dependence of the fifth and the seventh harmonic contains equal contributions of mono- and diatomic amplitudes ($A_{\text{mono}} \approx A_{\text{dia}}$ with a variation of 5% to 10%). However, for the third harmonic A_{mono} and A_{dia} evolve differently. While A_{mono} constantly exhibits values between 0.3 and 0.5 over the full range of intensities, A_{dia} sharply increases up to an SWIR intensity of $\sim 4.5 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ before following the same trend as A_{mono} at a slightly (~ 0.15) lower level. This intensity-dependent behavior is consis-

tent with the aforementioned transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry as shown in Fig. 2(a). Only for the third harmonic signal a significant difference in the harmonic yield between the monoatomic and diatomic nearest-neighbour directions was observed. We mainly attribute this to a stronger influence of Kerr-type harmonic generation even in the non-perturbative intensity regime for the third harmonic compared to higher orders that are dominated by non-perturbative processes which are less sensitive to the differences between mono- and diatomic directions. Consequently, at intensities near the threshold, both perturbative and non-perturbative processes generate similar third harmonic yields, leading to an intensity-dependent anisotropic θ -dependence of the third harmonic yield.

Figure 2(d) demonstrates how the transmission of the mean SWIR pulse (averaged over all orientation angles θ) decreases as the excitation intensity increases towards the laser-induced damage threshold of the MgO crystal. At the same time, the modulation amplitude (for the absorption $A_{\text{mono}} \approx A_{\text{dia}}$) of the eight-fold symmetry increases with intensity in a manner that is notably different from the intensity dependence of the amplitudes that were discussed in Fig. 2(c). This finding aligns with the observation that while nonlinear absorption is linked to the frequency conversion process, it contributes minimally to the overall transmission loss. Instead, the primary cause of these losses can be attributed to nonlinear photoionization, which plays a significant role in supplying the required seed electrons for high-harmonic generation (HHG).

We repeated the same experiments in bulk sapphire samples (150 μm thick) cut along the M-plane ($10\bar{1}0$) for which the projection of the hexagonal unit cell onto the M-plane exhibits a similar structure as MgO [see Fig. 3(d)]. For an excitation intensity of 18 TW cm^{-2} (damage threshold at $\sim 21 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$) we observe an eight-fold symmetry for all detected harmonic orders as well as for the nonlinear absorption of the fundamental SWIR laser pulse [see Fig. 3(a)]. Again, we observe maxima in the angular distribution of the SWIR absorption when the high-harmonic emission is maximized. Even though the orientation angles of the

Figure 3: Experimentally determined HHG and absorption in Al_2O_3 . (a). θ -dependence of HHG and SWIR absorption in Al_2O_3 at an excitation intensity of 18 TW cm^{-2} . Experimental datapoints are represented by circles while the solid lines show numerical fits according to Eq. 1. (b). Fitted amplitudes A_{mono} and A_{dia} as a function of the SWIR intensity. (c). Average transmission and modulation amplitude of the 8-fold symmetric transmission loss. Transmission values are averaged over all orientation angles, the errorbars represent the corresponding standard deviation. (d). Sketch of the projection of the hexagonal unit cell of an M-cut Al_2O_3 sample. (e). Ratio of the mono- and diatomic amplitudes extracted from the fit function (Eq. 1) showing the transition from a stronger A_{dia} to a stronger A_{mono} with increasing intensity, finally settling at $A_{dia} \sim A_{mono}$.

HHG and absorption maxima do not correspond to mono- and diatomic nearest-neighbour directions, we keep the terminology that was introduced in the MgO case. Figure 3(b) shows the modulation amplitudes extracted from Eq. 1 as a function of the SWIR peak intensity. Even at the lowest intensity of $\sim 4 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ the third harmonic signal exhibits an eight-fold symmetry resulting in comparable magnitudes of A_{mono} and A_{dia} [see blue circles and blue triangles in Fig. 3(b)]. For all observed harmonic orders A_{mono} and A_{dia} display a similar intensity dependence. We find a transition from a stronger diatomic amplitude for intensities below 12 TW cm^{-2} to a stronger monoatomic amplitude, before, at the highest measured intensities, the two amplitudes become equal again. This observation is confirmed by plotting the ratio $A_{\text{dia}}/A_{\text{mono}}$ in Fig. 3(e). The ratio changes from values ≥ 1 for excitation intensities up to 12 TW cm^{-2} to ratios ≤ 1 for intensities between 12 TW cm^{-2} and 18 TW cm^{-2} . This indicates that the emission from directional real-space charge oscillations towards monoatomic nearest-neighbours at $\theta = 45^\circ, 135^\circ, 225^\circ$ and 315° becomes more important than the emission from shorter diatomic nearest-neighbour directions at $\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270° for $I_0 \geq 12 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$. The transmission results obtained from the sapphire sample display the same characteristics as in the MgO case with the exception that A_{mono} is constantly slightly larger than A_{dia} [see Fig. 3(c)].

In order to verify the generality of our experimental approach we furthermore analyzed the angular dependence of the HHG process and the nonlinear absorption in wide-bandgap fluoride crystals. As a prominent example we used LiF crystals ($200 \mu\text{m}$ thickness) with a cubic crystal structure similar to the one of MgO [see inset in Fig. 4(a)]. Apart from the fact that no transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry was observed for the third harmonic, the results shown in Fig. 4 exhibit comparable characteristic features as in MgO. Both, the observed odd harmonic orders as well as the nonlinear absorption display an eight-fold symmetry in which the maxima of the HHG signal coincide with those of the SWIR absorption [Fig. 4(a)]. The angular contrast of the odd harmonics and of the absorption reaches comparable values as in the MgO case [see Fig. 4(b)] and the average transmission

shows the characteristic drop from the Fresnel-related losses at low intensity to lower values at higher intensity towards the damage threshold [see Fig. 4(c)].

The experimental results presented in this section provide consistent evidence for a corre-

Figure 4: Experimentally determined HHG and absorption in LiF. (a). θ -dependence of HHG and SWIR absorption in LiF. Experimental datapoints are represented by circles while the solid lines show numerical fits according to Eq. 1. (b). Fitted amplitudes A_{mono} and A_{dia} as a function of the SWIR intensity. (c). Average transmission and modulation amplitude of the 8-fold symmetric transmission loss. Transmission values are averaged over all orientation angles, the errorbars represent the corresponding standard deviation.

lation between the emission of high-order harmonics and nonlinear absorption of the SWIR pump laser pulse. In all investigated materials the harmonic emission was the strongest at orientation angles where also the nonlinear absorption was at its peak. We interpret these findings as an indication that ionization, which results from the nonlinear absorption, drives the maximization of the HHG process. In MgO a transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry was observed for the angular dependence of the third harmonic as the SWIR intensity increased. In Al₂O₃ all detected harmonic orders exhibited an eight-fold symmetry irrespective of the pump laser intensity. However, a change of the strongest emission - angles from $\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270° (called diatomic nearest-neighbour directions in the MgO

case) to $\theta = 45^\circ$, 135° , 225° and 315° (monoatomic nearest-neighbour directions) was identified.

Based on our experimental results we identified an unambiguous link between HHG and laser-induced nonlinear ionization. However, all widely discussed mechanisms for HHG in solids (interband recollision, intraband dynamics and ionization-related mechanisms) require the presence of quasi-free, excited electrons in the conduction bands. Hence, an unambiguous identification of the dominating HHG mechanism solely based on the presented experimental results is out of reach.

Results from numerical simulations and analytical model and discussion

To improve our understanding of the dominant HHG mechanism and of the observed θ -dependent features we performed numerical simulations based on the SBEs^{44,45} for the case of MgO. SBE-based calculations have demonstrated remarkable concordance with experimental high-harmonic spectra previously, rendering them indispensable for gaining profound understanding of carrier dynamics and high-harmonic generation (HHG) mechanisms in solid-state materials. Moreover, they offer valuable and detailed insights into these intricate processes. In our simulations we implement the band structure of MgO (taken from Ref.³²), using one valence and one conduction band) to estimate the θ -dependence of HHG by projecting the electric field of the SWIR pump laser pulse onto the $\Gamma - K$ and $\Gamma - X$ directions. We then calculate the resulting high-harmonic emission due to the interband polarization $P(\omega)$ and the intraband current $J(\omega)$ (details of the numerical model can be found in the Supporting Information). The relative contribution of the two competing mechanisms is displayed in Fig. 5(a). Strikingly, the intraband current (orange triangles) dominates the emission of H5, H7 and H9 for SWIR peak intensities $\geq 1 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ while for the third harmonic the

emission due to the interband polarization (dark circles) remains stronger. Thus, contrary to previous publications^{6,18,31,36,46} we do not observe a dominant intraband mechanism for all observed below-bandgap harmonics. Instead, for the third harmonic, our simulations indicate a transition from a prevailing intraband mechanism at 0.5 TW cm^{-2} to a stronger interband mechanism at a peak intensity of 10 TW cm^{-2} , while both contributions lead to comparable harmonic yields in between.

Figure 5: Numerical simulations of HHG in MgO using SBEs. (a). Relative importance of the interband polarization and the intraband current for the total HHG signal obtained by integrating the harmonic yields for $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$. (b) - (e). Orientation-dependence of the odd harmonics (H3-H9) for various SWIR peak intensities.

Figures 5(b)-(e) show the orientation-dependence of H3-H9 for four different SWIR peak intensities (0.5 TW cm^{-2} , 1 TW cm^{-2} , 5 TW cm^{-2} and 10 TW cm^{-2}). The angular distribution of H3 changes from a four-fold symmetry with maxima at $\theta = 45^\circ$, 135° , 225° and 315° (monoatomic nearest-neighbour directions) at $I_0 = 0.5 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ to an eight-fold symmetry at $I_0 = 1 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$. At even higher SWIR peak intensities a four-fold symmetry with maxima at $\theta = 0^\circ$, 90° , 180° and 270° (diatomic nearest-neighbour directions) develops. Comparing

these observations to Fig. 5(a) indicates that the θ -dependence associated with a dominating intraband mechanism (at $I_0 = 0.5 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$, four-fold symmetry with maxima along monoatomic nearest-neighbour directions) differs from the angular dependence due to the interband polarization (at $I_0 = 10 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$, four-fold symmetry with maxima along diatomic nearest-neighbour directions). Thus, the transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry corresponds to a transition from a purely intraband case to an intermediate situation where the combination of the interband polarization and the intraband current generates an eight-fold symmetry of the total H3 signal. The experimentally observed transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry of H3 (compare Fig. 2) could hence be interpreted as a result of such a combined emission.

The θ -dependence of H5 exhibits an eight-fold symmetry over the full range of SWIR intensities with one exception at $I_0 = 5 \text{ TW cm}^{-2}$ where the maxima along the diatomic nearest-neighbour directions break up into two peaks leading to a twelve-fold symmetry that was experimentally not observed. However, as the excitation intensity further increases up to 10 TW cm^{-2} , an eight-fold symmetry in good agreement with our measurements is observed again. In the intensity range where we could experimentally access the seventh harmonic, the numerical simulations based on the SBEs reproduce the constant eight-fold symmetry of H7 while H9 tends to display a four-fold symmetric angular dependence whose preferred orientation for efficient HHG varies between the diatomic and the monoatomic nearest-neighbour directions [see Fig. 5(e)].

Generally, several microscopic physical mechanisms contribute to the two observables [$P(\omega)$ and $J(\omega)$] in the SBE-calculations. While interband recollisions are expected to dominate the above-bandgap response of the interband polarization $P(\omega)$, high-harmonic generation due to the intraband current is usually associated with quasi-free carriers being accelerated to non-parabolic regions of the energy bands. However, other HHG mechanisms are naturally included in these two observables. In particular, ionization-related HHG mechanisms are expected to strongly contribute to the low-order harmonics.^{19,39}

We expect both, the Brunel mechanism and the injection current to contribute to the intraband current as they solely rely on the persistent population dynamics in a single band (i.e. the conduction band). The Brunel mechanism is traditionally associated with harmonic generation due to a nearly step-wise modulation of the carrier density in gases, clusters and solids while the injection current is directly connected to the spatial displacement of an electron during the excitation itself. As shown in a previous publication,²⁸ the injection current generally dominates over the Brunel mechanism at experimentally accessible intensities in solid-state materials. In contrast, the relative strength of HHG arising from band anharmonicity and the injection current has not been investigated up to now. A numerical estimate of the associated excursion lengths however, indicates that the injection current is at least as important as HHG due to band anharmonicity for the harmonic orders investigated in this work (see Supporting Information for details). In our current implementation of the SBEs, as is common practice for numerical feasibility, solely vertical transitions in momentum space (i.e. direct transitions) are included [see Fig. 6(a)]. Hence, in addition to the SBE-based numerical simulations we estimate the part of the angular dependence of the photoionization rate which arises from interatomic transitions between different atoms [see depiction of Wannier jumping in Fig. 6(a)].

This simple analytical model is not a full simulation in the Wannier basis and (but rather) an addition to the rigorous numerical approach via the SBEs. However, the analytical model allows accessing interatomic and this non-vertical transitions that are absent in our implementation of the SBEs. Our analysis is based on the dipole moments between the localized states, as described by the Wannier-basis functions.⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹ The dipole moments characterize the degree of overlap of the wavefunctions of electrons localized at the corresponding atoms. The angular dependence of the photoionization rate (i.e. the rate of transitions from the valence to the conduction band) is estimated by the multiphoton formalism⁵⁰ as

$$\Gamma \approx \sum_s |\vec{E} \cdot \vec{s}|^{2N(\vec{s})} d_s^{2N(\vec{s})} \quad (2)$$

where the sum is taken over the neighbouring atomic sites, $\vec{E} \cdot \vec{s}$ is the projection of the electric field on the direction towards the atomic site, and d_s is the transition dipole moment between a state in the valence zone and a state in the conduction zone at atomic site s . The electric field modifies the energy difference between these states and correspondingly the number of photons $N(\vec{s})$ that is needed for a multiphoton transition (for details see Supporting Information).

For MgO we calculated the transition dipole moment based on the known energy struc-

Figure 6: Numerical simulations of HHG in MgO using maximally-localized Wannier-functions. (a). Depiction of electronic excitation at a single atom (corresponding to a vertical transition in momentum space), to interatomic space and to neighbouring atoms (Wannier-Jumping, corresponding to a non-vertical transition in momentum space). (b). Orientation-dependence of the total photoionization rate calculated according to Eq. 2 for different SWIR laser intensities.

ture of the isolated atoms, the bandgap value and the interatomic distances. In MgO, the valence-zone electrons are localized at oxygen atoms. The conduction band electrons are partly delocalized in the interatomic space. The remaining localized part of the conduction band electron wavefunction resides mostly in the vicinity of the oxygen atoms.⁵¹ For the calculations of the angle-dependent photoionization rate we have taken nearest-neighbour O-O transitions (corresponding to $\theta = 45^\circ, 135^\circ, 225^\circ$ and 315°), second-nearest-neighbour O-O transitions (corresponding to $\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270°) and nearest-neighbour O-Mg transitions (corresponding to $\theta = 0^\circ, 90^\circ, 180^\circ$ and 270°) into account (see Fig. S6 and the

discussion in the Supporting Information for details). We only analyze the θ -dependence of the photoionization rate itself since all ionization-related harmonic orders are proportional to this rate and will inherit the same angular distribution. Numerical results for the θ -dependence of the ionization rate are presented in Fig. 6(b). At a low SWIR intensity of 2 TW cm^{-2} a four-fold symmetry with maxima along the monoatomic nearest-neighbour directions is observed. As the excitation intensity increases, a transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry is found in the θ -dependence of the photoionization rate [see orange line for a peak intensity of 13 TW cm^{-2} in Fig. 6(b)]. The additional maxima appearing at $\theta = 0^\circ$, 90° , 180° and 270° can be associated with ionization along the diatomic nearest-neighbour directions (excitation from an O ion to a Mg ion or vice versa).

Hence, our estimates of the angular dependence of the photoionization rate due to Wannier jumping exhibit qualitatively similar orientation dependencies as observed in our experiments and as predicted for the intraband current by the SBE calculations. Moreover, HHG due to the injection current is directly associated with nonlinear absorption of the fundamental field (in fact the injection current directly results from the losses of the fundamental field due to photoionization) which has been found to exhibit a positive correlation with the emission of high harmonics in the experiments. Given that both the injection current and the nonlinear current resulting from band anharmonicity exhibit comparable excursions of the excited carriers, the injection current emerges as a strong contender for generating below-bandgap harmonics associated with the intraband current. This observation underscores the significance of the injection current as a plausible mechanism contributing to the generation of below-bandgap harmonics in solid-state systems.

Conclusion

In summary, we have presented experimental and numerical results of the angular dependence of HHG in periodic crystals. To correlate the nonlinear frequency conversion pro-

cess to laser-induced ionization we performed simultaneous transmission measurements that provide information on the ionization yield at different crystallographic orientations. Our investigations were focused on bulk MgO crystals with a cubic crystal structure and were complemented by experimental investigations in Al₂O₃ and LiF. In all materials a distinct correlation between HHG and nonlinear ionization was observed which manifested itself in a well-defined orientation dependence of both signals. In detail, we observed maxima of the harmonic emission coinciding with maxima of the nonlinear absorption. We interpreted this as an enhanced HHG conversion efficiency at angles where laser-induced ionization is also maximized. A symmetry analysis of the angular dependence of the experimentally observed signals connected the angles of maximum HHG emission and SWIR absorption with monoatomic and diatomic nearest-neighbour directions in the crystal lattice.

To further substantiate our interpretation and investigate the dominant mechanisms responsible for HHG we performed numerical simulations based on the SBE using MgO as a model system. Our results reproduced the experimentally observed transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry of H3 at intermediate intensity while at high intensity the interband polarization was found to dominate. For H5 and H7, that according to the SBE calculations are dominated by the intraband current $J(\omega)$, an eight-fold symmetry was predicted in agreement with our experimental findings.

Since several microscopic mechanisms, including the nonlinear current due to band anharmonicity and the injection current, contribute to $J(\omega)$, we numerically investigated the possible influence of ionization-related HHG mechanisms on the experimentally detected harmonic spectra. Our results unveiled a transition from a four-fold to an eight-fold symmetry of the photoionization rate for increasing intensity where the strongest signal is predicted along the monoatomic nearest neighbour directions. According to the SBE calculations, the intraband current is confirmed as the dominant source of the observed harmonics. Additionally, our estimates of Wannier jumping demonstrate consistency with the orientation dependencies observed in our experiments and the predicted behavior of the intraband current from SBE

calculations. Furthermore, in our experimental results we identified a positive correlation between the nonlinear absorption (which is directly associated with the injection current) of the fundamental field and the emission of high harmonics. Both the injection current and the nonlinear current resulting from band anharmonicity induce comparable excursions of excited carriers. As a result, the injection current emerges as a strong contender for generating below-bandgap harmonics associated with the intraband current, underscoring its significant role as a plausible mechanism for generating such harmonics in solid-state systems. These findings collectively enhance our understanding of the underlying processes driving high-harmonic generation and contribute to the broader understanding of nonlinear optical phenomena in solid-state systems. Further investigations exploring the intricate interplay between injection currents, intraband dynamics, and harmonic emission are warranted for a more comprehensive understanding of these phenomena. In addition, our experimental methodology presents an extraordinary instrument for elucidating the prevailing microscopic HHG mechanisms in crystalline specimens, utilizing discernible orientation dependencies. Moreover, the suggested methodology can be readily applied to 2D-materials, which hold significant relevance in the field of optoelectronic applications. The presented correlation of harmonic generation efficiencies with interatomic symmetries facilitates the customization of crystalline materials to optimize harmonic yield. Our approach can be further applied in future research to investigate symmetry dynamics in photoexcited crystals through time- and angle-resolved measurements.

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Supporting Information Available

Supporting Information available: Description of experimental procedures and detailed information on the numerical model. This material is available free of charge via the internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>

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TOC Graphic

For Table of Contents Use Only

Linking High-Harmonic Generation and Strong-Field Ionization in Bulk Crystals

Peter Jürgens, Sylvianne D.C. Roscam Abbing, Mark Mero, Clara L. Garcia, Graham G. Brown, Marc J.J. Vrakking, Alexandre Mermillod-Blondin, Peter M. Kraus and Anton Husakou

The accompanying image illustrates the key experimental finding of our manuscript: a direct correlation between the orientation-dependent high-harmonic emission and nonlinear absorption in a bulk MgO crystal. The figure also includes a schematic representation of various excitation pathways that are held responsible for the intensity-dependent anisotropic features.